

Influence of Customer Relationship Management Program on Purchase Interest at Starbucks in Application Use

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Abstract:- This research is submitted in hopes of helping the reader in searching information about Application Starbucks Indonesia and as terms for the researcher to get a bachelor degree. In this research, a method that used is descriptive quantitative with simple linear regression. The questioner is spread by a Google form system with 111 total people of respondent with 17 statements. In this research it looks like that Application Starbucks Indonesia user with a CRM program on buying interest at Starbucks Pos Pengumben is 44,5%. CRM (Customer Relationship Management) variable in this Application Starbucks Indonesia in Starbucks Pos Pengumben has an average score of X 4,571 that mean is very good. In buying interest variable at Starbucks that has an average score of Y 4,54 that mean is very good.

Keywords:- CRM (Customer Relationship Management), Application Starbucks Indonesia, Buying Interest, Application.

I. INTRODUCTION

Along with the advancement of human Civilization, life and human needs continue to experience changes as if there is no end. Technological advances play a major role in human life. Along with the development of technology, humans are also evolving and adapting to changes that occur today to meet the needs of food, lifestyle and many other things. So that the most advanced technology is, the more people need these things to facilitate future.

The development of technology in the Industrial revolution 4.0 is growing very rapidly, which changes the behavior and attitudes of the community in general in meeting needs, thus creating new business opportunities, and making it easier for people to sell online.

By selling online, communication between sellers and buyers become very easy and smooth, so that misunderstandings can be resolved quickly, well and easily, this opportunity is realized by business people to use the

internet in doing business. The internet also makes it easier to communicate from one location to another, making it easier for virtual teams to develop, produce and market products.

Behind the convenience and advantages of The 4.0 industrial revolution, there are weaknesses, including the threat of unemployment of workers, because nowadays it is completely automated and there are also many fake news or hoaxes due to the easy dissemination of information, therefore on the other hand there is a need for resource development. Human or humanities so that these negative impacts can be suppressed.

In 2020, technology is very supportive in everyday life, different from the previous 10 years, where service applications such as delivering food, goods and people to their destination are still not popular in smartphone applications as well as electronic payments. Currently, there are many mainstay applications such as OVO, DANA, GO-PAY, JENIUS and M-BANKING BCA.

With the emergence of these applications and over time, many food and beverage outlets have created special applications for their own outlets to make it easier for consumers to use these applications.

In addition to being easier and more Practical to use, consumers also get the latest information about products and attractive benefits. This has prompted Starbucks Indonesia to create an application to help consumers buy Starbucks products.

Currently, coffee consumption has become a trend in the daily life of Indonesian people. Not only coffee, there are also other trending drinks such as bubble drinks, tea drinks and more, which can be found from low-end, middle-class and high- end brands such as Starbucks.

Starbucks places their stores as premium Brands that rely on the unique taste of coffee, they not only focus on products but also facilities and a comfortable place.

In order to make it easier for customers, Starbucks issued the Starbucks Indonesia application in which there was a Starbucks card which was originally a physical card. This Starbucks Indonesia application is included in CRM (Customer Relationship Management) with the aim of managing the sales process from pre-sales to post-sales within the company to get responses from consumers. In the Starbucks Indonesia application, which can be downloaded from the Playstore and App Store for free, in this application, consumers can register their personal data and create an electronic card to pay, without the need to pay with physical money and access information at Starbucks in Indonesia.

This electronic payment system on the Starbucks Indonesia Application is very useful for the community, especially coffee lovers. During this Covid-19 pandemic, the government in Indonesia implemented a PSBB (Large-Scale Social Restriction) policy to prevent the spread of the Covid-19 virus, therefore many companies and traders are using applications to sell online.

❖ *Theory of Basic*

➤ *Understanding Buying Interest*

Buying interest is the tendency of consumers to buy a brand or take actions related to purchases as measured by the level of possibility of consumers to make purchases according to Dadan Mubarak (2016).

According to Adi & Widiyanto (2013) Explaining the definition of buying interest is an integration process that combines knowledge to evaluate two or more alternative behaviors and choose one of them. The result of this integration process is a choice, which is presented cognitively as a desire to behave.

According to Wicaksono (2015) buying interest is an impulse that arises in a person to buy goods or services in order to fulfill their needs.

➤ *Buying Interest Indicator*

In the buying interest indicator, the researcher uses

Helmi's (2016) indicators, the indicators are as follows:

- **Transactional interest**, namely the tendency of a person to buy a product. That is, consumers already have an interest in making a purchase of a certain desired product.
- **Referential interest**, namely the tendency of a person to refer products to others, the point is where when a consumer buys a product and is satisfied with the product he gets and the consumer recommends the product to others.
- **Preferential Interest**, which is an interest that describes the behavior of someone who has a main preference for the product, meaning that consumers will return to buy products that have been made a top priority even though there are many other products.
- **Explorative Interest**, namely this buying interest describes the behavior of someone who is always looking for information about the product he is interested in and looking for information to support the positive characteristics of the product.

The point of this theory is that consumers always feel interested in finding the latest information on the product.

➤ *Buying Interest Aspect*

According to Levisa (2020) said that the aspects contained in buying interest include:

- **Attention**, namely the existence of great attention from consumers to a product, either goods or services.
- **Interest**, namely after the attention it will arise a sense of interest in consumers.
- **Desire**, namely the feeling to want or have a product.
- **Confidence**, namely the individual's belief in the product, causing a decision (final process) to obtain it with an action called buying.
- **Decisions**, namely consumer behavior in making buying decisions considering what goods and services to buy, where, when, how, in what amount, and why to buy these products.

➤ *Stages of Buying Interest*

According to Binalay et. al (2016), in the stages of consumer buying interest there is a concept, namely the AIDA concept including:

• *Attention*

The initial stage in assessing a product or service that is needed by prospective customers, where at this stage the prospective customer learns the value of the products / services offered.

• *Interest*

Interest of prospective customers arises after getting more detailed information observing the product / service.

• *Desire*

Prospective customers think about and discuss what causes the desire and desire to buy the products / services offered. In this stage, prospective customers must advance and level from just being interested in the product. This stage is characterized by a strong desire from potential customers to buy and try the product.

• *Action*

Make passive decisions on bids. At this stage, prospective customers who have visited the company will have a level of stability in buying or using a product offered.

Phase Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

According to Purwanto et. al (2018), CRM consists of the following phases:

- **Get new customers (Acquire):** New customers are obtained by providing easy access to information, new innovations, and attractive services
- **Increasing customer value (Enhance):** The company seeks to establish relationships with customers through providing good service to its customers (customer service).
- **Retain existing customers (Retain):** Retain profitable customers, by offering what is needed by specific customers rather than what is needed by market customers, because the value of the product or service to customers

is the proactive value that best suits their needs. The focus of the company at this time is how to retain existing customers will definitely provide benefits for the company rather than how to get new customers that are not necessarily profitable.

❖ *Factors Influencing Buying Interest*

According to Widiastuti (2017) explains that there are several factors that influence consumer buying interest, namely as follows:

- **Differences in work**, meaning that with differences in one's work it can be estimated that interest in the level of work he wants to achieve, the activities carried out, the use of his free time, and others.
- **Socio-economic differences**, meaning that someone who has a high socioeconomic status will more easily achieve what he or she wants than someone with a low socioeconomic status.
- **Differences in hobbies or hobbies**, meaning how a person uses his spare time.
- **Gender differences**, meaning that women's interests will be different from those of men, for example in shopping patterns.
- **Age difference**, meaning that the ages of children, adolescents, adults and parents will have different interests in an item, object activity and a person.

The other factors that influence buying interest are:

- *Cultural factors*
- ✓ **Culture**, is the most basic determinant of a person's desires and behavior. If the lower beings' behavior is largely governed by instinct, then human behavior is largely learned.
- ✓ **Sub Culture**, which has smaller sub-cultural groups which are identification and socialization that are unique to the behavior of their members. There are four kinds of sub-cultures, namely national groups, religious groups, racial groups and geographical areas.
- ✓ **Sub-culture**, which has smaller sub-cultural groups which are identification and socialization that are unique to the behavior of their members. There are four kinds of sub-cultures, namely national groups, religious groups, racial groups and geographical areas.
- ✓ **Social class**, namely groups in society, where each group tends to have the same values, interests and behavior.
- *Social factors*
- ✓ **Reference groups**, namely groups that have a direct or indirect influence on a person's attitudes and behavior.
- ✓ **Family**, namely family members can have a strong influence on buyer behavior.
- ✓ **Role and Status**, namely the position of a person in each group can be explained in terms of role and status.
- *Personal Factors*
- ✓ **Age and Life Cycle Stage**, namely a person's purchases of goods and services will change during his life. Likewise, a person's taste is related to his age.
- ✓ **Jobs**, namely with the existence of work groups, companies can produce products according to the needs of certain work groups.

- ✓ **Economic conditions**, namely the economic condition of a person can be seen from the level of income that can affect the choice of products.
- ✓ **Lifestyle**, which can be interpreted as a person's pattern of life that is revealed in his activities, interests and opinions that are formed through a social class and work..
- ✓ **Personality and Self-Concept**, namely personality is a psychological characteristic that distinguishes each person while the self-concept is more towards self-image.

• *Psychological Factors*

- ✓ **Motivation**, which is a need that is strong enough to direct a person to seek satisfaction with that need.
- ✓ **Perception**, namely the process of individuals selecting, formulating, and interpreting input information from the five senses to create a meaningful picture of the world.
- ✓ **Learning**, which describes changes in the behavior of an individual that comes from experience.
- ✓ **Trust**, which is a descriptive idea that someone has about something.
- ✓ **Attitude**, which is a person's point of view on something.

➤ *Understanding Customer Relationship Management (CRM)*

Referring to Laura (2019), customer relationship management (CRM) is a process of managing detailed information about each customer and carefully managing all aspects needed by customers to maximize customer loyalty. Therefore, CRM requires further technology in implementing it, such as the use of computer-based data.

Meanwhile, according to Hidayat (2014), CRM refers to system software that helps companies obtain and store customer data and establish two- way relationships.

➤ *Approach in Customer Relationship Management (CRM)*

Kotler & Keller (2012), There are three approaches that companies can take to maintain and develop customer relationships, namely:

➤ *Financial benefits*

Financial benefits include cost savings incurred by a customer when buying products or services from the company. The most frequent implementation of providing financial benefits is by running frequency marketing programs such as giving rewards in the form of special discounts to customers who frequently make purchases or when they buy in large quantities. For example, if Starbucks Indonesia customers buy Starbucks products, they will get "stars" rewards from the application, so they can be exchanged for drinks or products provided by Starbucks for free or other attractive promos.

➤ *Social benefits*

The provision of social benefits touches the needs and desires of customers more personally. The easiest implementation of providing social benefits is remembering the customer's name. This has been widely applied by various companies, employees will greet customers and be able to remember what services they like from customers based

on the existing database. For example, by downloading the Starbucks Indonesia application, the application will enter consumer personal data into the database on the Starbucks Indonesia application, so that the customer transaction history in buying products can be recorded and remembered by Starbucks employees at the selected Starbucks outlet, which is in the Starbucks Indonesia application. . Another benefit of structural ties is in the form of customization benefits. Customization benefits received by customers may include customer perceptions of preferential treatment, special attention or individual rewards, and special services that are not provided to other customers.

➤ *Objectives of Customer Relationship Management (CRM)*

According to Dyantina et. al (2012) The purpose of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is basically to increase customer resilience and satisfaction. In general it can be said that the goal of any CRM strategy is to develop profitable relationships with customers. The main goal of CRM is to increase the long-term growth and profitability of the company through a better understanding of customer behavior.

➤ *CRM goals include:*

- Knowing customer needs in the future.
- Assist the company in improving the better service that can be provided to customers
- Get new customers
- Knowing the improvements needed by the company in order to satisfy customers
- Able to analyze customer behavior
- Reduce costs incurred in order to get new customers because with CRM companies can hold old customers to remain loyal to the company.

➤ *Benefits of Customer Relationship Management (CRM)*

The benefits obtained from the application of CRM according to Kusuma (2010) include:

- Enable sales by developing customer history and profiles.
 - Supporting services through assurance management.
 - Troubleshooting and troubleshooting.
 - *Cross Selling*, namely selling products that customers need based on their purchases.
 - *Upgrading* is to offer a higher customer status.
 - Attract new customers by offering personalized service
 - Keeping existing customers Other benefits that can be obtained from implementing CRM:
- ✓ Provide convenience for consumers to conduct business or transactions with companies.
 - ✓ CRM can focus on the end customer for products and services.
 - ✓ Redesign business processes face to face with consumers.
 - ✓ Increase company profit
 - ✓ Build a consumer loyalty.

❖ *Fase Customer Relationship Management (CRM)*

According to Purwanto et. al (2018), CRM consists of the following phases :

• *Getting new customers (Acquire):*

New customers are obtained by providing easy access to information, new innovations, and attractive services.

• *Increase customer value (Enhance):*

The company tries to establish relationships with customers through providing good service to its customers (customer service).

• *Maintain existing customers (Retain)*

Retain profitable customers, by offering what specific customers need instead of what market customers need, because the value of the product or service to the customer is the proactive value that best suits their needs.

The focus of the company at this time is how to retain existing customers will definitely provide benefits for the company rather than how to get new customers that are not necessarily profitable.

➤ *Application Definition*

According to Wahyuni (2020), an application is a ready-to-use program that can be used to execute commands from users of the application with the aim of getting more accurate results in accordance with the purpose of making the application. Applications have the meaning of solving problems using one of the application data processing techniques that usually race a desired or expected computation or expected data processing. According to Wahyuni (2020), an application is a ready-to-use program that can be used to execute commands from users of the application with the aim of getting more accurate results in accordance with the purpose of making the application. Applications have the meaning of solving problems using one of the application data processing techniques that usually race a desired or expected computation or expected data processing.

Application classification can be classified into several classes, including:

- **Enterprise software is an application used by** companies to organize company activities.
- **Enterprise infrastructure software is an** application created to provide the general capabilities needed to support enterprise software (enterprise software).
- **Information worker software** is an application commonly used to address individual needs to create and process information. Generally for individual tasks within a department.
- **Content access software** is an application that is commonly used to access content without editing, but may include software that allows editing of content. Such software addresses the needs of individuals and groups to consume digital entertainment and publish digital content.

- **Educational software** is an application that is almost the same as Media and Entertainment Software (Content access Software) but usually displays different content.
- **Media development software** is an application used to address individual needs to produce print and electronic media, generally in the commercial or educational field.
- **Product engineering software** is an application commonly used for hardware and software product development.

Fig 1:- Mindset

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used in this research is descriptive quantitative. The data of this research are in the form of questionnaires to consumers of Starbucks Indonesia at Starbucks Pos Pengumben outlets, Jl. Raya Pos Pengumben No. 34A RT.10/RW.3 Srengseng, Kembangan District, West Jakarta.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ How to Register the Starbucks Indonesia Application

In registering a Starbucks Indonesia account on a smartphone, there are several steps as follows:

- Download the Starbucks app via playstore or appstore
- Register. Open the Starbucks Indonesia application that has been downloaded, this application is green with a white Starbucks logo. Click "sign up" then fill in according to the application instructions listed.
- Select the registration type. There are 2 types of registration, namely "I do not have a Starbucks card" for consumers who do not have a Starbucks card, "I have a Starbucks card" for consumers who already have a Starbucks card. If the consumer already has a Starbucks card, the consumer will be asked to enter the card number and Starbucks account security code.
- After pressing the sign up button, complete the consumer's date of birth after that, slide the "Terms of Use" button to the right. The button will turn green. This indicates that the consumer has read and agreed to the terms of use of the Starbucks Indonesia application. Tap create account (iPhone) or Join Rewards (Android). This button is at the bottom of the page. Starbucks Indonesia account will be successfully created if all the question fields have been filled in and meet the requirements.

➤ Payment Using the Starbucks Indonesia App

Consumers no longer need to pay for Starbucks products using physical money, but consumers only need to pay by pressing the pay button on the Starbucks Indonesia home menu, then a barcode appears to be scanned at the nearest Starbucks outlet.

- The first step is to click the "Pay" button
- The second step, a barcode appears to be scanned at Starbucks outlets and the transaction is complete.

➤ Data Analysis/Characteristics of Respondents

• Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

This means that consumers strongly agree because in the Starbucks Indonesia application there is a way to see the nearest location and can see the menus at Starbucks, as well as access to provide input in the application section through the customer care menu.

Fig 2:- Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

• Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

Fig 3:- Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

• Characteristics of Respondents Based on Occupation

Fig 4:- Characteristics of Respondents Based on Occupation

- *Ease of accessing the Starbucks Indonesia application.*

Based on the statement above, 1 respondent (0.9%) chose to disagree, 4 respondents (3.6%) chose not to agree, 35 respondents (31.5%) chose to agree, 71 respondents (64%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 of the 71 respondents chose strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because all ways to get information, payment methods, view products and promos are all already available and complete in the Starbucks Indonesia application.

- *Starbucks employees name exclusively and specifically in order to provide good service.*

Based on the statement above that 2 respondents (1.8%) chose to disagree, 19 respondents (17.1%) chose not to agree, 49 respondents (44.1%) chose to agree, 41 respondents (36.9%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 of 49 respondents chose to agree. This means that consumers agree because if consumers often visit Starbucks outlets and transact with the Starbucks Indonesia application, consumer data will be recorded by the system at the outlet. So that when consumers return to the outlet, the barista will recognize and greet consumers who frequently

- ❖ *CRM (Customer Relationship Management)*

- *Getting New Customers (Acquire)*

- *Up-to-date information by the Starbucks Indonesia application in buying Starbucks products.*

Based on the statement above, 7 respondents (6.3%) chose not to agree, 21 respondents (18.9%) chose to agree, 83 respondents (74.8%) strongly agreed. These results indicate that as many as 111 of the 83 respondents chose strongly agree. This means that Starbucks consumers strongly agree because the Starbucks Indonesia application always updates the latest information every day and offers attractive promos.

- *Using the Starbucks Indonesia application because of new innovations*

The statement above states that 2 respondents (1.8%) chose to disagree, 3 respondents (2.7%) chose not to agree, 37 respondents (33.3%) chose to agree, 69 respondents (62.2%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 of 69 respondents chose strongly agree. transact at the outlet.

- *Using the Starbucks Indonesia application because it provides a birthday treat in the form of a birthday cake reward and a star bonus.*

The statement above that 1 respondent (0.9%) chose to disagree, 9 respondents (8.1%) chose not to agree, 22 respondents (19.8%) chose to agree, 79 respondents (71.2%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 79 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because the consumer's personal data has been registered in the Starbucks Indonesia application so that if the consumer has a birthday, the Starbucks application will provide a special treat in the form of free cakes and other benefits.

- *Using the Starbucks Indonesia application because you can access new seasonal items (special menus in certain months) exclusively, such as new drinks and bar merchandise.*

The statement above states that there are 7 respondents (6.3%) who choose less agree, 29 respondents (26.1%) choose agree, 75 respondents (67.6%) choose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 75 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers who use the Starbucks Indonesia application get the opportunity given to access the latest seasonal menus and merchandise every month from the Starbucks company.

- *Using the Starbucks Indonesia application because it is given a reward in the form of "stars".*

The statement above states that 5 respondents (4.5%) chose not to agree, 28 respondents (25.2%) chose to agree, 78 respondents (70.3%) chose to strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 78 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because if consumers often buy Starbucks products through the Starbucks Indonesia application, they will get a reward in the form of stars which if collected can be exchanged for special gifts.

- *Using the Starbucks Indonesia application because it provides attractive offers to consumers*

Based on the statement above, it states that 4 respondents (3.6%) chose not to agree, 33 respondents (29.7%) chose to agree, 74 respondents (66.7%) chose to strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 74 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers feel strongly agree because the Starbucks Indonesia application provides many benefits for consumers who join as members of the Starbucks Indonesia application compared to those who do not.

- *Given the convenience of transacting in the Starbucks Indonesia application*

The statement above states that 2 respondents (1.8%) chose to disagree, 4 respondents (3.6%) said they did not agree, 26 respondents (23.4%) chose to agree, 79 respondents (71.2%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 79 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers feel very agreeable because in the Starbucks Indonesia application, they make payments only by scanning the barcode without having to spend physical money and there is no need to find it difficult to find cash and change from Starbucks (cashless).

The highest average result is found in X1 of (4.68), namely respondents are interested in using the Starbucks Indonesia application because the Starbucks Indonesia application always updates the latest information every day and offers attractive promos. Meanwhile, there are also the lowest average results in X4 of (4.16), namely Starbucks employees mention names exclusively and specifically in order to provide good service, because sometimes the baristas at Starbucks forget to mention the names of consumers because many consumers order.

➤ *Buying Interest (Transactional Interest)*

- *Have an interest in using the Starbucks Indonesia application in purchasing Starbucks products.*

The statement above states that 5 respondents (4.5%) chose not to agree, 29 respondents (26.1%) chose to agree, 77 respondents (69.4%) chose to strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 of the 77 respondents chose strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because the Starbucks Indonesia application is more practical and efficient in purchasing Starbucks products.

- *Have an interest in buying Starbucks products using the Starbucks Indonesia application because it is faster with complete application features.*

The statement above states that 7 respondents (6.3%) chose not to agree, 33 respondents (29.7%) chose to agree, 71 respondents (64%) chose to strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 of the 71 respondents chose strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because consumers do not need to open other applications and everything is complete in the Starbucks Indonesia application.

➤ *Buying Interest (Referential Interest)*

- *Satisfied and will recommend the Starbucks Indonesia application to friends and family in purchasing Starbucks products.*

The statement above states that 1 respondent (0.9%) chose to disagree, 7 respondents (6.3%) chose not to agree, 39 respondents (35.1%) chose to agree, 64 respondents (57.7%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 of 64 respondents chose strongly agree. Because the Starbucks Indonesia application provides many promo benefits and consumers will feel the application is worthy of being recommended to their closest friends and family.

- *Inviting other consumers to purchase Starbucks products through the Starbucks Indonesia application*

The statement above states that 2 respondents (1.8%) disagreed, 9 respondents (8.1%) said they did not agree, 37 respondents (33.3%) chose to agree, 63 respondents (56.85%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 of the 63 respondents chose strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because consumers no longer need to queue long in terms of transacting Starbucks products.

➤ *Buying Interest (Preferential Interest)*

- *Choose the Starbucks Indonesia application as a top priority in purchasing Starbucks products.*

Based on the statement above states that 1 respondent (0.9%) chose strongly disagree, 1 respondent (0.9%) chose to disagree, 10 respondents (9%) chose not to agree, 37 respondents (33.3%) chose to agree, 62 respondents (55.9%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 62 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because consumers feel comfortable using the Starbucks Indonesia application compared to other applications in purchasing Starbucks products

- *Feel comfortable and safe in purchasing Starbucks products by using the Starbucks Indonesia application.*

Based on the statement above, it states that 4 respondents (3.6%) chose not to agree, 39 respondents (35.1%) chose to agree, 68 respondents (61.3%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 68 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because consumers already feel comfortable and safe to use the Starbucks Indonesia application compared to other applications because the data is stored securely in the Starbucks system itself, because there is a verification PIN.

➤ *Buying Interest (Explorative Interest)*

- *Follow the latest information about Starbucks products in the Starbucks Indonesia application.*

The statement above states that 7 respondents (6.3%) chose to disagree, 34 respondents (30.6%) chose not to agree, 70 respondents (63.1%) chose to strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 70 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because every day Starbucks always updates the latest information about the latest products.

- *Follow the latest information about attractive promos offered by the Starbucks Indonesia application.*

The statement above states that 1 respondent (0.9%) chose strongly disagree, 1 respondent (0.9%) chose to disagree, 5 respondents (4.5%) chose not to agree, 31 respondents (27.9%) chose to agree, 73 respondents (65.5%) chose strongly agree. These results indicate that as many as 111 out of 73 voted strongly agree. This means that consumers strongly agree because the Starbucks Indonesia application always provides the latest interesting promos.

The highest average result is in X1, where respondents are interested in using the Starbucks Indonesia application because the Starbucks Indonesia application always updates the latest information every day and offers attractive promos. Meanwhile, there are also the lowest average results in X4, namely Starbucks employees mention names exclusively and specifically in order to provide good service, because sometimes the barista at Starbucks forgets to mention the customer's name because many consumers order.

The highest average result is Y1 (4.65), that is, respondents have an interest in using the Starbucks Indonesia application because the application is very easy to use and more practical, all features are complete in one application. Meanwhile, there are also the lowest average results at Y5 (4.42), namely I chose the Starbucks Indonesia application as a top priority in purchasing Starbucks products, because many other CRM applications also provide more complete features than the Starbucks Indonesia application.

The correlation results get a value of 0.667, that between CRM (Customer Relationship Management) in this case the Starbucks Indonesia application and buying interest has a strong relationship, because CRM in the Starbucks Indonesia application makes it easy for consumers to see information - information and promos and also very practical use. in terms

of payment and provide benefits in the form of rewards and other exclusive offers. This can be interpreted that the use of the Starbucks Indonesia application is strongly related to

Starbucks buying interest at Starbucks Pos Pengumben outlets.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.667 a	0.445	0.440	2.652
a Predictors: (Constant), y				

Table 1:- Results

Source: Primary Data Processing Results 2020

From the table above, it can be seen that R square is 0.445. Can be seen with the formula:

$$KD = r^2 \times 100\%$$

$$KD = 0,445 \times 100\%$$

$$KD = 44,5\%$$

This shows that the use of the Starbucks Indonesia application on Starbucks purchase intention has an effect of 44.5%.

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

- That the average result of X is 4,571, very good category. This means that the CRM (Customer Relationship Management) in the Starbucks Indonesia Application is very good.
- That the mean result of Y is 4.54, including the very good category. Interest in buying at Starbucks outlets is very good.
- From the coefficient of determination test of 44.5%.

B. Suggestion

- Starbucks wants to further improve the culture of greeting customers and mentioning the customer's name in order to provide better service, because the culture of greeting is a small thing of a service that makes consumers more valued. In addition, the Starbucks Indonesia application should further improve more features and attractive promos so that Starbucks consumers in Indonesia use the Starbucks Indonesia application itself compared to other applications.
- For further research, it is recommended to add other variables that have not been covered in this study, such as service quality, product quality sold by Starbucks and so on.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdurrahman M, Muhidin SA, Somantri A. 2011. Dasar-Dasar Metode Statistika Untuk Penelitian. Bandung (ID): Pustaka Setia
- [2]. Adi, R. N., & WIDIYANTO, I. (2013). *Analisis Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Keputusan Pembelian dengan Sistem Pre Order secara Online (Studi Kasus pada Online Shop Chopper Jersey)* (Doctoral dissertation, Fakultas Ekonomika dan Bisnis)
- [3]. Binalay, A. G., Mandey, S. L., & Mintardjo, C. M. (2016). Pengaruh Sikap, Norma Subjektif dan Motivasi terhadap Minat Beli Secara Online Pada Mahasiswa Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis di Manado. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 4(1)
- [4]. Dyantina, O., Afrina, M., & Ibrahim, A. (2012). Penerapan Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Berbasis Web (Studi Kasus Pada Sistem Informasi Pemasaran di Toko YEN-YEN). *Jurnal Sistem Informasi (JSI)*, 4(2), 516-529.
- [5]. Ghozali, I. (2016). Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 23 (Edisi 8). Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [6]. Hidayat, R. (2014). Sistem Informasi Ekspedisi Barang Dengan Metode E-CRM Untuk Meningkatkan Pelayanan Pelanggan. *Jurnal Sisfotek Global*, 4(2).
- [7]. Juliansyah Noor, S. E. (2016). *Metodologi Penelitian: Skripsi, Tesis, Disertasi & Karya Ilmiah*. Prenada Media.
- [8]. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Marketing management 14th ed.* New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall, Inc.
- [9]. Kusuma, Debbi. 2010. "4 Manfaat Utama dari Customer Relationship Management System." *Journal of Management*, 1(3), p 46-49.
- [10]. Laura, D. (2019). *Pengaruh Program Customer Relationship Management (CRM) terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan Starbucks: Survei pada Pengguna Layanan Starbucks Card* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Multimedia Nusantara).
- [11]. Sugiyono. (2010). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. Bandung: PT Alfabeta.
- [12]. Wicaksono, S. A. (2015). *Pengaruh merek dan desain terhadap minat beli konsumen* (Doctoral Dissertation, UNIVERSITAS NEGERI SEMARANG).
- [13]. Widiastuti, O. (2017). *Hubungan Antara Persepsi Terhadap Kualitas Produk Dengan Minat Beli Bedak Muka SARIAYU pada Mahasiswi di Universitas Mercu Buana Yogyakarta* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Mecu Buana Yogyakarta).
- [14]. Yuliara, I. M. (2016). *Regresi linier sederhana*. 13.